

DIRECT NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF DAMAGE PROGRESSION IN LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATES USING MULTI-SCALE MODELLING

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1 Abstract:

The specific characteristics of composite material, such as light-weight, high strength, corrosive resistance, make it one of the most appealing materials to be used for various applications. At the same time, understanding their failure behaviour due to the composition of two or more constituents poses enormous challenge. One of such studies is the damage progress in the composite laminates. Therefore, this paper focuses on the development of a unique computational model capable of determining the ultimate strength of open-hole laminated composite plate under tension. Direct numerical simulation (DNS) of composites was developed and integrated into the in-house developed finite element (FE) code DIAMOND/IPSAP and the progressive failure analysis (PFA) was carried out using element failure method (EFM) as the computational scheme and micromechanics based failure criteria.

2 Background:

2.1 Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS)

Several researches based on the macroscopic approach have been performed during the recent years. However, understanding and predicting the mechanism of the failure initiation turned out to be indirect since the failure of composite materials initiates from the microscopic level and then propagates to the macroscopic level [1]. Also the information like the influence of an individual fibre on the mechanical behaviour will disappear in the macro-scale modelling. Therefore, there exists necessity to realize micro-scale modelling to completely understand the different aspect of composites. In order to achieve such goal, this paper

introduces DNS of the composites using the clustered cell modelling.

DNS of the composites can be performed by using either a unit cell or a clustered cell model. The cluster cell model has significant advantage over the unit cell model. For example, the unit cell model approach has the limitations of predicting the local behaviour of the constituents of composite materials which is not the case with the clustered cell model approach. As noted in Kim et al. [1], by using the clustered cell model the microscopic level stress distribution as well as failure initiation can be investigated conveniently. Also its simulation can be carried out without any assumption of local bending or local boundary conditions. It was also successfully demonstrated that the effect of non-uniform arrangements of constituents from defect or irregularity can be taken into account with ease. However, this will be more limited to achieve by using the unit cell and macroscopic approach. A typical figure depicting the unit cell as well as clustered cell model is shown in Fig. 1. This paper discusses both the unit cell approach and the clustered cell modelling approach.

2.2 Micromechanics of Failure (MMF)

Due to the material and geometric inhomogeneity arising from the inclusion of the fibres in the fibre reinforced composites, non-uniform micro-stresses at the constituent level is developed by external mechanical and thermal loadings. For each fibre, matrix or fibre-matrix interface region, ply failure can have different failure mechanisms. Therefore, proper failure criteria should be used to distinguish where failure initiates. Due to the lack of information about the macro-stress/strain and micro-stress/strain

relation, prediction of the constituent failure will be a difficulty [2]. The relation is generally expressed in terms of the stress amplification factor, as in Equations (1)-(2).

$$\sigma = M_\sigma \bar{\sigma} + A_\sigma \Delta T \quad (1)$$

$$t = M_t \bar{\sigma} + A_t \Delta T \quad (2)$$

$$M_\sigma = \begin{bmatrix} M_{11} & M_{12} & M_{13} & M_{14} & 0 & 0 \\ M_{21} & M_{22} & M_{23} & M_{24} & 0 & 0 \\ M_{31} & M_{32} & M_{33} & M_{34} & 0 & 0 \\ M_{41} & M_{42} & M_{43} & M_{44} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & M_{55} & M_{56} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & M_{65} & M_{66} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$A_\sigma = [A_1 \quad A_2 \quad A_3 \quad A_4 \quad 0 \quad 0]^T$$

The stress amplification factor was calculated using the direct finite element analysis with the unit cell model.

Failure criterion can be expressed in terms of the micro level strength, as in Equations (3)-(5)

-Fibre failure criterion

$$-C_f < \sigma_x < T_f \quad (3)$$

-Matrix failure criterion

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_{VM}}{\sigma_{VM}^{cr}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{I_1}{I_1^{cr}}\right) = 1 \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_{VM}^{cr} = T_m \left(\frac{\alpha^2 + \alpha}{\alpha + 1}\right)^{1/2}, \quad I_1^{cr} = T_m \frac{\alpha^2 + \alpha}{\alpha^2 - 1}, \quad \alpha = C_m / T_m$$

-Fibre-Matrix Interface failure criterion

$$\left(\frac{t_n}{Y_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{t_s}{Y_s}\right)^2 = 1 \quad (5)$$

σ_{VM} is von Mises equivalent stress. I_1 is volumetric stress invariant. T_f , C_f , T_m , C_m , Y_n and Y_s are micro level strengths.

Micro level strength was obtained from the macro level strength of a ply using the proper failure criteria and a detailed distribution of micro stresses.

$$T_f = \max\left(M_{\sigma 11,f}^{(i)} X_T + A_{\sigma 1,f}^{(i)} \Delta T\right) \quad (6)$$

$$C_f = \max\left(-M_{\sigma 11,f}^{(i)} X_C + A_{\sigma 1,f}^{(i)} \Delta T\right) \quad (7)$$

Figure 3 is a flow chart to obtain the matrix micro strength. Equivalence stress, σ_{eq} is,

$$\sigma_{eq} = \frac{(\alpha - 1)I_1 + \sqrt{(\alpha - 1)^2 I_1^2 + 4\alpha \sigma_{VM}^2}}{2\alpha} \quad (8)$$

$$p = \sigma_{eq} / T_m$$

Stress amplification factor can be obtained using DNS(Direct Numerical Simulation). In DNS,

RVE(Representative Volume Element) model is used. To represent the micro level behaviour, periodic boundary condition is applied on RVE model. Periodic boundary condition can be expressed as in Equation (9).

$$u_i^{+j} - u_i^{-j} = c_i^j \quad (9)$$

where, u_i^j indicates the displacement along the i-direction of one node located at the boundary face whose normal vector is along the j-direction.

2.3 Element Failure Method (EFM)

Element-failure algorithm, proposed by Beissel et al. [3] is a basic concept which deals with the analysis of dynamic crack propagation. In this technique, the elements through which crack propagates, loses the ability to sustain deviatoric and tensile volumetric stresses; i.e. they are failed as shown in Fig 2 [3]. These failed elements are not removed from the mesh, but rather a set of external nodal forces are applied on the failed elements. No requirements of remeshing or the definition of new contact surfaces as well as the allowance of crack propagation in any direction are cited as its main advantage [3].

In this paper, EFM as implemented by Tay et al. [4] is used as a computational platform for the progression of damage throughout the finite element (FE) model with the micro-mechanics based failure criterion as shown in Fig. 4 instead of the more traditional material properties/stiffness degradation method (MPDM).

Before beginning the EFM procedure, linear elastic analysis is conducted on the FE model to find the initiation of damage using proper failure criteria. Whenever a failed element is detected the EFM is employed to simulate the progression of damage in the model. Since, the basic idea of EFM is to modify the nodal force of a failed element to represent the state of damage in the composite material [4], the external forces will be applied until the net nodal forces of adjacent elements approaches zero. The external forces to be applied are unknown and are calculated through the iterative procedure which is implemented into the present IPSAP FE-code. Since, the micromechanics based failure criteria distinguishes between the matrix and fibre failure mode, a special care is taken while applying the external force when either of them fails. When the matrix only fails, an external force will be applied in the transverse direction to the fibre and its properties

be degraded. Similar is the case with the occurrence of failure in the fibre, where the properties of fibre are degraded. If both of them fails completely, the model cannot sustain any load and the external force is applied in both fibre and matrix direction until the assigned convergence criteria is satisfied. If there is no failed element detected, the applied load is increased by small increment at each step. The main advantage of using EFM over MPDM is that it assures computational convergence and stability as the stiffness matrix is not altered in EFM. This also results in saving the computational time and effort [4]. In this paper, the prediction of damage progression in laminated composite plate is conducted within the micromechanical FE model where fibres and matrices are modelled explicitly.

3 Model Description:

The tensile loaded carbon fibre reinforced plastic (CFRP) with centrally located hole is modelled in DIAMOND. The dimension of the laminate with open hole is taken from the study done by Arunkumar and Przekop [5]. The dimensions of the specimen is 254mm × 63.5mm with centrally located hole of diameter 12.7mm. The material used in this paper is different from the one used by Arunkumar because of the unavailability of micromechanical properties of IM7/8552. The composite plate is therefore made of IM7/8551-7 with the three different stacking sequence. The thickness of the laminate with their respective lay-up configuration is also shown in Table 1. The material properties are shown in Table 1. The properties of the matrix, fibre as well as the lamina are obtained from WWFE-II (PART A) [6].

The finite element model for composite plate with hole is prepared using DIAMOND as shown in Fig 6. The model consists of two dimensional shell elements and is relatively fine meshed around the hole with 4,920 as the total number of elements. The left end of the model is completely fixed and a tensile load is applied to the right end. The applied load is increased at each step of the iteration until the laminate fails completely. The unit cell model with three dimensional solid elements is created using the recently implemented direct numerical simulation generator (DNSG) in DIAMOND as shown in Fig 4. The micro strength and stress amplification factor data are calculated using the unit cell model and transferred to IPSAP to perform the progressive failure analysis using EFM.

The stiffness values for fibre can also be calculated by using the rule of mixture as in Equation (10) [7].

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{E}_1 &= E_{f1}V_f + E_mV_m \\ \bar{\nu}_{21} &= \nu_{f21}V_f + \nu_mV_m \\ \frac{1}{\bar{E}_2} &= \left(\frac{1}{E_{f2}}\right)V_f + \left(\frac{1}{E_m}\right)V_m \\ \frac{1}{\bar{G}_{12}} &= \left(\frac{1}{G_{f12}}\right)V_f + \left(\frac{1}{G_m}\right)V_m \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

4 Results and Discussion

The results obtained are plotted using the present DIAMOND as the post processor. The failure distribution in matrix and fibre for each layer are shown in Fig (7) and (8), respectively. The first ply failure load and the last ply failure load are predicted for each lay-up configuration and are shown in Table 3. Since, there are not any experimental data available for the material used in this paper, it will be uneasy to verify the results obtained immediately.

However, the results can be obtained by using macro level strength failure criteria like maximum stress failure criterion with EFM and are compared with the one obtained from MSC Nastran using one of the available macro level failure criteria like Hill failure criterion.

5 Conclusion and Further Study

The PFA with EFM as the computational scheme is developed in IPSAP and the results obtained are presented in this paper. The results obtained from the developed algorithm will be verified experimentally in the future. Also, the effect of random fibre arrangement in composite structure can be taken into account through the developed DNSG.

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References

- [1] S.J. Kim, C.S. Lee, H.J. Yeo, J.H. Kim and J.Y. Cho “Direct numerical simulation of composite

structures". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 36, No. 24, pp 2765-2785, 2002.

- [2] S.K. Ha, K.K. Jin and Y.C. Huang "Micro-mechanics of failure (MMF) for continuous fibre reinforced composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 42, No. 18, pp 1873-1895, 2008.
- [3] S.R. Beissel, G.R. Johnson and C.H. Popelar "An element-failure algorithm for dynamic crack propagation in general directions". *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, Vol. 61, Issues 3-4, pp 407-425, 1998.
- [4] T.E. Tay, G. Liu, V.B.C. Tan, X.S. Sun, and D.C. Pham "Progressive failure analysis of composites".

Fig. 1. Description of the clustered and unit cell approach.

Fig 2: Crack path model of the element-failure algorithm.

Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 42, No. 18, pp 1921-1966, 2008.

- [5] S. Arunkumar, and A. Przekop "Predicting failure progression and failure loads in composite open-hole tension coupons". NASA/CR-2010-216700, 2010.
- [6] A.S. Kaddour and M. J. Hinton "Input data for test cases used in benchmarking triaxial failure theories of composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, 2012.
- [7] K.K. Jin, Y.C. Huang, Y.H. Lee and S.K. Ha "Distribution of micro stresses and interfacial tractions in unidirectional composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 42, No. 18, pp 1825-1849, 2008.

Fig. 3: Process of obtaining matrix's micro strength.

Fig 4: Unit cell model generated in DIAMOND.

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Fig. 5: Implementation of the present EFM with MMF.

Fig 6: Finite element model of laminated composite plate created in DIAMOND.

(a)

(b)

(c)

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Fig 7: Matrix Failure Distribution in open hole laminate at (a) layer 1 - 45° , (b) layer 2 - 90° , (c) layer 3 - -45° and (d) layer 4 - 0° where red coloured elements are failed.

(d)

Fig 8: Fibre Failure Distribution in open hole laminate at (a) layer 1 - 45° , (b) layer 2 - 90° , (c) layer 3 - -45° and (d) layer 4 - 0° .

Table 1: Stacking sequence of the present model

Stacking Sequence	Thickness (mm)
$[45/90/-45/90]_s$	0.96012
$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/90_2]_s$	1.96088
$[45_4/90_4/-45_4/90_4]_s$	4.23164

Table 3: First ply failure (FPF) load and last ply failure (LPF) load for each configuration

Stacking Sequence	FPF (N)	LPF (N)
$[45/90/-45/90]_s$	7,800	20,100
$[45_2/90_2/-45_2/90_2]_s$	15,600	40,200
$[45_4/90_4/-45_4/90_4]_s$	34,020	118,260

Table 2: Material properties of IM7/8551-7

Stiffness	Matrix	8551-7	
	E_m	4.08E+09	Pa
	G_m	1.48E+09	Pa
	ν_m	0.38	
	Fibre	IM7	
	E_{f11}	2.76E+11	Pa
	E_{f22}	1.90E+10	Pa
	G_{f12}	2.70E+10	Pa
	ν_{f12}	0.20	
	G_{f23}	7.00E+09	
	Lamina	IM7/8551-7	
	E_{11}	1.65E+11	Pa
	E_{22}	8.40E+09	Pa
	$G_{12} = G_{13}$	5.60E+09	Pa
	G_{23}	2.80E+09	Pa
ν_{12}	0.34		
fibre volume fraction	0.60		
Strength	X	2.56E+09	Pa
	X'	1.59E+09	Pa
	Y	7.30E+07	Pa
	Y'	1.85E+08	Pa
	S	9.00E+07	Pa